

1 **MoS₂ nanosheets for improving analytical performance of lactate biosensors**

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16

17 **Abstract**

18 In this paper, a new 2D lactate electrochemical biosensor was developed. It was
19 based on the incorporation of molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) platelets, obtained by an
20 exfoliation method, onto the surface of a glassy carbon (GC) electrode, together with
21 lactate oxidase enzyme (LOx). For the sensor construction, conditions regarding the
22 exfoliation solvent type, as well as both the size and amount of MoS₂, were optimized.
23 The biosensor platform (GC/MoS₂/LOx) was topographically characterized by atomic
24 force microscopy (AFM) and the charge transfer process occurring at the electrode
25 interface was studied by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The
26 GC/MoS₂/LOx biosensor was applied to the determination of lactate in presence of
27 hydroxymethylferrocene (HMF) as a redox mediator. Electrocatalytic effect of the
28 system MoS₂/LOx was evaluated by comparing the cyclic voltammetric biosensor
29 response with those obtained for biosensors incorporating only one of the components
30 (MoS₂ or LOx) onto the electrode surface. Biosensors containing both components
31 exhibit the best electrocatalytic response. From the calibration curve obtained at +0.30
32 V, the following analytical parameters were obtained: linear concentration range from
33 0.056 to 0.77 mM, high sensitivity (6.2 μA mM⁻¹), good detection limit (17 μM) and
34 reproducibility (RSD = 4.7%).

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36

37 **Keywords:** molybdenum disulfide, electrochemical biosensor, lactate oxidase, cyclic
38 voltammetry, atomic force microscopy, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy.

39

40 **1. Introduction**

41 The employment of 2D nanomaterials, such as graphene, for the development of
42 enzymatic based biosensors has attracted great attention during the last decade as a way
43 to obtain devices with improved analytical performance [1–3]. The excellent graphene
44 properties enable the implementation of the detection. In particular, graphene modified
45 electrodes offer a high surface area to load a high amount of enzymes, increasing
46 sensitivity. Moreover, in the case of electrochemical biosensors, the excellent graphene
47 conductivity facilitates the redox transfer between the enzyme and the electrode surface
48 [4,5]. In a natural further step, the incorporation of other recently discovered 2D
49 materials into biosensing devices, such as the transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs),
50 is of potential interest [6,7,8]. TMDs are graphene analogues formed by stacking S-TM-
51 S sheets through Van der Waals forces. As a result of the weak forces between layers,
52 single or few layers of these materials can be easily exfoliated from the bulk by
53 mechanical cleavage, sonication in common solvents or ion intercalation/sonication
54 methods, among others [9,10]. Due to their interesting mechanical, electrical and optical
55 properties, the resulting 2D materials nanosheets have been studied and profusely
56 applied in catalysis, energy storage and electronics [11–15]. TMDs application to
57 sensing purposes is a current trend that lies on the large surface area and fast electron
58 transfer of these materials. However, compared with the above-mentioned applications,
59 the employment of TMDs nanosheets in sensing devices is still scarce, being almost
60 exclusively focused on molybdenum disulfide [16–19]. In this sense, several groups
61 have constructed MoS₂ based electrochemical sensors for detecting compounds such as
62 glucose [20–22], dopamine [23,24], eugenol [25], tryptophan [16,26] and bisphenol
63 [27,28]. The good analytical properties obtained for these sensors evidence that the use
64 of MoS₂ is a promising strategy for determining compounds of interest. In contrast, the

65 employment of TMDs for developing electrochemical enzymatic biosensors remains
66 almost unexplored. Among the developed TMDs based electrochemical biosensing
67 platforms, the majority involved the use of MoS₂ nanosheets and the enzyme glucose
68 oxidase [29–31]. Beyond glucose oxidase, implemented MoS₂ based biosensors
69 involving laccase [32] and horseradish peroxidase [33] have been also reported,
70 allowing the determination of caffeic acid and hydrogen peroxide, respectively.
71 Recently, Pumera et al. have demonstrated that the employment of TMDs in enzymatic
72 biosensors for electrochemical detection of the pesticide fenitrothion, via an inhibition
73 pathway, offers enhanced responses in comparison with biosensors without TMDs [34].
74 The satisfactory analytical properties obtained in the above-mentioned studies indicate
75 that TMDs, particularly MoS₂, present good biocompatibility allowing also a high
76 enzyme loading. Therefore, they are promising candidates for biosensing.

77 In the present work, we study the effect of incorporating MoS₂ into biosensing
78 platforms for lactate determination. The development of implemented biosensors for the
79 determination of lactate is of great interest in several fields such as clinical diagnostics,
80 food industry and fermentation processes. In the literature, we can find electrochemical
81 lactate enzymatic biosensors based on the employment of nanomaterials with different
82 dimensionality, such as metal nanoparticles [35–37], diamond nanoparticles [38–40],
83 graphene oxide [41], reduced graphene [42–45] or carbon nanotubes [46–48]. However,
84 as far as we know, there are no biosensors for lactate determination that include only
85 TMDs and lactate oxidase. In order to develop the biosensing platform, we have
86 obtained MoS₂ sheets by exfoliation in different solvents and we have deposited them,
87 together with lactate oxidase, on a glassy carbon (GC) electrode surface. Once the
88 optimum conditions regarding the exfoliation solvent and both the size and amount of
89 MoS₂ were established, the topographical surface of the MoS₂/GC was imaged by

90 atomic force microscopy (AFM). The biosensor was employed for lactate determination
91 in order to prove that MoS₂ offers a good platform for lactate oxidase accommodation
92 leading to an enhancement of the biosensing performance.

93

94 **2. Experimental Section**

95 **2.1. Materials**

96 Molybdenum disulfide (99%, 2 μm and 90 nm in size), Lactate oxidase (LOx, EC
97 232-841-6 from *Pediococcus* species) lyophilized powder containing 41 units / mg
98 solid, L-(+)-lactic acid lithium salt 97%, dopamine, hydroxymethyl-ferrocene (HMF),
99 N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP), dimethylformamide (DMF), ethanol (EtOH), isopropyl
100 alcohol (IPA), potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide, ascorbic acid, uric acid
101 and citric acid were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (www.sigmaaldrich.com). Lactate
102 oxidase stock solutions were prepared dissolving 1.3 mg of the LOx lyophilized powder
103 in 250 μL of 0.1M phosphate buffer solution (pH = 7.0), aliquoted (10 μL) and stored at
104 -30°C. Under these conditions, the enzymatic activity remains stable for several weeks.
105 Buffer solutions were prepared using sodium phosphate from Merck (www.merck.com).
106 All solutions were prepared just prior to use with purified water obtained from a
107 Millipore Milli-Q-System (www.millipore.com).

108 **2.2. Experimental techniques**

109 Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies
110 were performed with an Ecochemie Autolab PGSTAT302 N system (Utrecht, The
111 Netherlands, www.ecochemie.nl). The electrochemical cell consisted of an Ag/AgCl
112 (Metrohm, 3.0 M KCl) reference electrode, a platinum auxiliary electrode and a bare or
113 modified glassy carbon working electrode (3 mm internal diameter). Cyclic
114 voltammetry was carried out using the biosensors in the presence of HMF (which acts

115 as soluble mediator in solution) and in the presence or absence of L-lactate. Solutions
116 were deaerated with nitrogen gas before use, and the gas flow was kept over the
117 solutions during experiments.

118 EIS experiments were performed in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution (pH = 7),
119 containing 10 mM $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 / \text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. A sinusoidal potential modulation of ± 10 mV
120 amplitude in the 10^5 Hz- 10^{-2} Hz frequency range, spaced logarithmically (120 per 8
121 decades), was superimposed onto the formal potential of the redox couple, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$.

122 Atomic force microscopy (AFM) studies were carried out using two different
123 systems, a Nanoscope IIIa (Veeco) equipment and an Agilent 5500 Picoplus. Both
124 systems were employed for topographical analysis, while the last one was used for
125 single-pass Kelvin Force Microscopy (KFM) imaging. For morphological studies,
126 silicon cantilevers with nominal force constant of 40 N/m and radius of curvature of 8
127 nm were employed and the dynamic mode was employed (Blucker). The KFM data
128 were obtained with ANSCM-PT cantilevers (from AppNano), which have a force
129 constant in the 1-5 N/m range and nominal radius of curvature less than 30 nm. In the
130 KFM measurements, the sample was grounded. KFM measures the Contact Potential
131 Difference (CPD), which is the difference between the work function values of the
132 imaged sample location and that of the tip. The images taken with the Veeco equipment
133 had 512 x 512 pixels whereas those obtained with Picoplus had 1024 x 1024 or 4096 x
134 4096 pixels.

135 **2.3. Procedures**

136 **2.3.1. Synthesis of MoS_2 platelets**

137 MoS_2 atomic layers were synthesized from MoS_2 nano-sized as starting materials
138 through liquid exfoliation, following adapted published procedures [49–51]. We have
139 employed four different solvents such as NMP, DMF, EtOH/water and IPA/water. The

140 last two mixtures in a 45:55 v/v ratio. Briefly, 25, 50, 75 or 100 mg of the commercial
141 MoS₂ powder (90 nm or 2 μm in size) were mixed under sonication for 2 hours with
142 10.0 mL of the corresponding solvent. Since several authors [49-51] have demonstrated
143 that sophisticated ultrasonic equipment to obtain MoS₂ sheets with a high dispersion
144 degree are not necessary, the sonication procedure was carried out using a JP Selecta
145 ultrasonic bath sonicator at nominal power output of 100 W. After sonication,
146 dispersions were maintained 24 hours at 4°C and then centrifuged at 1500 rpm during
147 45 minutes. The supernatant was collected for its use in the GC electrode surface
148 modification.

149 **2.3.2. Preparation of the electrochemical sensors**

150 Glassy carbon electrode surfaces were polished with 1 μm diamond paste (Buehler)
151 and rinsed with water. GC electrodes were then modified by placing 10 μL of MoS₂
152 exfoliated in NMP, DMF, EtOH/water or IPA/water solvent, leaving air-dry and finally
153 5 μL of the LOx stock solution were dropped on this surface and left to dry.

154 Sensors containing only MoS₂ or LOx were obtained by modifying the GC electrode
155 with 10 or 5 μL respectively of the corresponding solution and leaving air-dry it.

156 **2.3.3. Evaluation of the electrochemical sensors**

157 Evaluation of all electrochemical sensors were carried out by substituting the natural
158 electron acceptor (O₂) by an artificial mediator (hydroxymethylferrocene, HMF), in the
159 following reaction catalysed by the enzyme LOx: Lactate + O₂ → Pyruvate + H₂O₂.
160 This strategy allows following the electrochemical behaviour of HMF at +0.30 V,
161 instead of detecting the generated hydrogen peroxide. Consequently, the contribution of
162 interfering substances, which could be oxidized at the high potential required for H₂O₂
163 detection, are minimized.

164 As can be observed in scheme 1, the enzyme catalyzes the oxidation of lactate to
165 pyruvate, while the electrons involved in the process are immediately transferred to the
166 oxidized form of the soluble redox mediator (HMF), regenerating the enzyme activity.
167 The re-oxidation of HMF on the electrode surface leads to a bioelectrocatalytic response
168 that can be observed, which is proportional to the amount of lactate present in the
169 solution. Therefore, in the absence of lactic acid, the typical redox response of the
170 ferrocene/ferrocinium process at +0.30 V in aqueous media is expected. The addition of
171 lactic acid will lead to an enhancement of the anodic peak current concomitant with a
172 decrease of the cathodic peak current as long as the sensor components give rise to an
173 electrocatalytic effect.

174 ***2.3.4. Preparation of the samples for AFM measurements***

175 Samples for AFM measurements were prepared by placing 10 μL of MoS_2 exfoliated
176 in NMP onto Si surfaces, left to dry and finally 5 μL of the LOx stock solution were
177 dropped on it. Sensors containing only MoS_2 were obtained by modifying the Si surface
178 with 10 μL of MoS_2 exfoliated in NMP. Likewise, additional samples were prepared by
179 depositing a drop of the solvent NMP (10 μL) in a flat silicon surface and let dry. In the
180 AFM experiments, samples containing 2 μm MoS_2 particles were analysed.

181

182 **3. Results and discussion**

183 **3.1. Parameters optimization for biosensor construction**

184 ***3.1.1. Exfoliation of MoS_2 in different solvents.***

185 According to Coleman et al. [49-51] in order to produce stable MoS_2 sheet
186 dispersions through sonication in a liquid medium, it is convenient to use solvents with
187 surface energies similar to those of the material to be exfoliated. Taking into account
188 both that the surface energy of MoS_2 is about 70 mJ m^{-2} and that the liquid surface

189 energy values of the solvents are around 30 mJ m^{-2} above their surface tensions, we
190 have selected the following four solvents: NMP, DMF, IPA/water and EtOH/water.
191 These solvents have the following surface tensions: 40.7 mN m^{-1} (NMP), 34.4 mN m^{-1}
192 (DMF), 22.3 mN m^{-1} (EtOH), 20.8 mN m^{-1} (IPA) and 72.8 mN m^{-1} (H_2O) (the units mN
193 m^{-1} and mJ m^{-2} are equivalent). In order to evaluate them, samples containing 75 mg of
194 molybdenum disulfide were exfoliated in 10.0 mL of the solvent tested. Afterwards,
195 cyclic voltammograms of four modified electrodes, prepared with MoS_2 exfoliated in
196 the different solvents and LOx (GC/ MoS_2 /LOx), were recorded in a 0.1 M $\text{pH} = 7.0$
197 phosphate buffer containing 1.0 mM HMF. A typical cyclic voltammogram is shown in
198 Figure 1, curve a, for the ferrocene/ferrocinium process at GC/ MoS_2 /LOx modified
199 electrode with a formal potential of $+0.30 \text{ V}$. Similar voltammograms are obtained for
200 all the solvents tested in absence of lactate (here it is only shown that obtained using
201 NMP to exfoliate the MoS_2). In presence of 0.65 mM L-lactate (Figure 1, curves b-e),
202 for the different solvents employed: IPA/water (b), EtOH/water (c), DMF (d) and NMP
203 (e), it is observed both an enhancement of the anodic peak current and a decrease of the
204 cathodic peak current, which is consistent with a clear electrocatalytic effect. However,
205 this enhancement is higher when NMP is used as solvent (curve e), with a threefold
206 increase in the anodic peak current with respect to curve a. Results confirm that the
207 solvent selection is fundamental for obtaining adequate MoS_2 sheet dispersions and, in
208 this sense, the most suitable solvent is NMP with a surface energy about 70.7 mJ m^{-2} ,
209 which is the most similar to the MoS_2 surface energy (70 mJ m^{-2}). Consequently, NMP
210 was selected as the most adequate exfoliating solvent to obtain MoS_2 sheet dispersions.

211 ***3.1.2. Selection of the MoS_2 powder particle size.***

212 Once the exfoliating solvent to obtain MoS_2 sheet dispersions was chosen, two
213 different MoS_2 powder particle sizes, 90 nm and $2 \mu\text{m}$, were compared in order to

214 obtain the most suitable sensor. Figure 2 shows voltammograms obtained for two
215 different GC electrodes modified with LOx and MoS₂ of 2 μm (curve b) or 90 nm
216 (curve c) in NMP in the presence of lactate. Similar voltammograms are obtained for
217 the two sizes tested in absence of lactate (here it is shown that obtained using 90 nm
218 MoS₂ powder nanoparticle size, curve a). In presence of lactate, it is clearly observed, in
219 both cases, an increase of the anodic peak current with respect to this current in absence
220 of lactate (curve a) with an increase of about 2.3 and 3 times for 2 μm and 90 nm,
221 respectively. The fact that the 90 nm MoS₂ based biosensor leads to a different response
222 that the 2 μm MoS₂ one is not surprising, since according to some authors, interaction
223 between nanoparticles and biological material are influenced by the nanomaterial
224 particle size [52]. It is worth noting that in the mild sonication conditions used, it will be
225 easier to obtain more adequate dispersions from a smaller particle size. Therefore, 90
226 nm MoS₂ was chosen as nanoparticle size for the following studies.

227 ***3.1.3. Selection of the concentration of MoS₂ dispersions.***

228 It was also expected that the MoS₂/LOx amount ratio in the modified electrode surfaces
229 could affect the enhancement of the anodic peak current due to the electrocatalytic
230 effect. In this sense, different amounts of 90 nm MoS₂ were exfoliated with 10.0 mL of
231 NMP, as it is explained in the *Procedures* section, and the resulting dispersions used to
232 modify the GC electrode surface together with a fixed amount of enzyme. Intensities of
233 the anodic peak current of modified GC electrodes measured at +0.30 V are shown in
234 Figure 3.

235 From this figure, it can be seen that as the concentration of MoS₂ increases, the peak
236 current intensity also increases up to a value of MoS₂ concentration of 7.5 mg mL⁻¹,
237 from which the peak current intensity decreases slightly. Accordingly, this
238 concentration is chosen for the preparation of the modified electrodes. A reason for this

239 behavior could be that the increase of MoS₂ amount leads to an increase in the specific
240 surface area and therefore in the loaded enzyme amount. However, up to a certain
241 concentration value, in our case around 7.5 mg mL⁻¹, the great amount of MoS₂ makes
242 more difficult the electron transfer on the electrode surface.

243

244 **3.2. Morphological characterization: AFM measurements**

245 In order to address the morphological study of the MoS₂ surfaces, a first step consisted
246 in analyzing the features, if any, associated just to the solvent employed for MoS₂
247 exfoliation. For this purpose, we deposited a drop of the solvent in a flat silicon surface
248 and let it dry. This surface was imaged and a characteristic image is shown in Figure 4a.
249 Clearly, many morphological features are due to the solvent. The most usual ones are
250 the rounded structures that appear scattered on the surface, particularly at the middle
251 right part of the image, that have an average size of 170 nm and heights in the 10-15 nm
252 range. In addition, brighter and wider spots are also found, as those two at the top part
253 of the image as well as those found at the bottom part, with sizes close to 500 nm and
254 heights larger than 50 nm. Finally, large corrugated aggregates as large as 7 microns and
255 with heights in the 70-100 nm range are also imaged as that located at the top left part
256 of the figure.

257 This rich morphology due just to the solvent employed poses a problem when trying to
258 image the MoS₂ flakes prepared with this solvent in the surfaces. A good criterion to
259 locate the MoS₂ structures consists in searching for plateau-like, 2D, structures and
260 heights in the nanometer range, such as those shown in Figure 4b. In this figure up to
261 seven such 2D structures are located. The surface profile along three of them (solid line)
262 is shown in Figure 4c. From these data we can assess that their height is close to 1 nm
263 and the lateral size between 300 and 600 nm.

264 Furthermore, in order to show that the imaged flakes are different from the rounded
265 structures coming from the solvent, we have performed KFM measurements with the
266 goal to detect a different contrast in the contact potential difference (CPD) in both
267 regions. With this purpose, we have chosen to image a larger 2D flake because of the
268 relatively large radius of the KFM tip. Thus, Figures 4d and 4e show a topographical
269 image of a flake and its corresponding KFM image, respectively. Clearly, the CPD
270 contrast is smaller at the flake than at the rounded structure due to the solvent. This fact
271 then confirms that the flakes are not structures associated to the solvent.

272 Finally, we have also imaged by AFM under ambient conditions the sample containing
273 both MoS₂ exfoliated in NMP and LOx (Figures 4 f-h). First, in Figure 4f is shown a
274 large MoS₂ flake, with a height close to 2 nm, in whose top surface are found globular
275 structures with lateral sizes in the 15 nm range and heights close to 3 nm as shown in
276 Figure 4g. Taking into account that the tip convolution effects increases the lateral size
277 and the tip load deforms vertically the soft structure, these dimensions are compatible
278 with those of the LOx. Figure 4h corresponds to other sample in which now the MoS₂
279 flakes are smaller with heights close to 3 nm. Similar globular structures are found on
280 the plateaus and in many cases practically cover the whole flake.

281

282 **3.3. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies**

283 EIS measurements have been performed in order to study the charge transfer process
284 occurring at the electrode interface. Figure 5 shows Nyquist diagrams for GC,
285 GC/MoS₂, GC/LOx and GC/MoS₂/LOx systems. Semicircles correspond to the charge
286 transfer resistance limiting process (R_{CT}) that is associated with the surface/electrolyte
287 interface. The linear part corresponds to the diffusion-controlled process. The electron-
288 transfer resistance (R_{CT}) obtained from these Nyquist plots for a bare GC electrode was

289 565 Ω . When the electrode is modified only with LOx or MoS₂, this value increases
290 dramatically, reaching 78,560 Ω and 154,000 Ω , respectively. For both cases, the
291 electron transfer between the redox probe, [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} and the glassy carbon electrode
292 surface is hampered, particularly for the GC/MoS₂ system. However, when the GC
293 electrode is modified simultaneously with MoS₂ and LOx, an intermediate R_{CT} value is
294 obtained (112,000 Ω), demonstrating that the presence of the enzyme diminishes the
295 high electron transfer resistance provided by MoS₂. This behaviour has been previously
296 observed in other enzymatic biosensing systems [53-55].

297 **3.4. Response of the GC/MoS₂/LOx sensor towards increasing L-lactate** 298 **concentrations**

299 Figure 6 shows the cyclic voltammograms of GC/MoS₂/LOx obtained for 1 mM
300 HMF in the presence of increasing lactate concentrations (A) and the corresponding
301 calibration curve (B) obtained from measurements of the current intensity at +0.30 V.
302 The analytical properties, linear response, sensitivity as well as detection and
303 quantification limits of the biosensor are obtained from the linear part of this calibration
304 curve. As it can be seen, the calibration plot is linear over a concentration range from
305 0.056 to 0.77 mM, according to the following equation $I (\mu\text{A}) = 0.19 (\pm 0.05) + 6.2$
306 $(\pm 0.1) C (\text{mM})$, with a correlation coefficient of 0.996. The sensitivity, calculated as the
307 slope of the calibration curve, is 6.2 $\mu\text{A mM}^{-1}$. The detection and quantification limits,
308 obtained as the ratio between three and ten times the standard deviation of the blank
309 signal and the sensitivity, are 17 μM and 56 μM , respectively.

310 The reproducibility was evaluated from the relative standard deviation (R.S.D. %)
311 for four different biosensors at 0.25 mM lactate concentration level, obtaining a value of
312 4.7%.

313 According to previous studies [41, 43], the presence of just LOx on the GC electrode
314 surface leads to a slight increment of the electrochemical analytical signal of 1 mM
315 HMF in presence of L-lactate with respect to the same electrode in absence of L-lactate.
316 Moreover, the response of bare GC and GC/MoS₂ electrodes are similar (data not
317 shown). As expected, due to the absence of the enzyme, none of them do show any
318 catalytic effect in presence of L-lactate. In contrast, the response of GC/MoS₂/LOx is
319 clearly better, which confirms that the combined presence of MoS₂ and LOx leads to an
320 improved response. A possible explanation can be that the presence of MoS₂ induces a
321 different positioning of the enzyme onto the electrode surface compared with that
322 adopted on bare GC surface, leading to a conformational stabilization of the enzyme in
323 a more adequate microenvironment and therefore to a higher functionality of the enzyme.

324 Table 1 shows the analytical properties of several lactate biosensors found in the
325 literature [35–48]. As it can be observed, the developed biosensor shows similar
326 analytical properties than those obtained for other biosensors also based in
327 nanomaterials. However, it is worth noting that, as far as we know, there are not similar
328 works in the literature that include only MoS₂ and the enzyme LOx together for lactate
329 determination. From this point of view, this work demonstrates for the first time the
330 synergistic effect of MoS₂ nanosheets and lactate oxidase in biosensing. Moreover, our
331 simple biosensor design just requires the inclusion of MoS₂ as nanomaterial while most
332 of the biosensors displayed in the table require a combination of different nanomaterials
333 in their design.

334 In order to evaluate the applicability of the biosensor, we have studied dopamine,
335 ascorbic acid, uric acid and citric acid as potential interferents. Results, displayed in
336 table 2, show an increase of the analytical signal about 10% for a ratio
337 [interferent]/[lactate] of 0.25, 0.53, 1 and 3, respectively.

338

339 **4. Conclusions**

340 We have developed an electrochemical biosensor based on the incorporation of MoS₂
341 platelets, obtained by an exfoliation method, onto the surface of a glassy carbon
342 electrode, together with lactate oxidase enzyme. The best biosensor response is obtained
343 using NMP as exfoliation solvent and 7.5 mg mL⁻¹ of MoS₂ with a particle size of 90
344 nm. AFM images show that MoS₂ structures consist in 2D structures with lateral sizes
345 between 300 and 600 nm and heights close to 1 nm. EIS studies show that when the
346 electrode is modified only with MoS₂, the electron transfer resistance value increases
347 dramatically. In contrast, the combined presence of MoS₂ and LOx in the biosensor
348 platform diminishes this high electron transfer resistance and leads to an enhanced
349 electrocatalytic response towards increasing lactate concentrations. Good analytical
350 parameters such as linear concentration range, sensitivity, detection and quantification
351 limits are obtained in a simpler biosensor construction than many similar biosensors
352 based on nanomaterials described in the literature.

353

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358

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539
540
541

542 **CAPTION OF FIGURES**

543
544 **Scheme 1.** Lactate detection principle.

545
546 **Figure 1.** CV response of GC electrodes modified with MoS₂/LOx in contact with 0.1
547 M pH = 7 phosphate buffer containing 1 mM of HMF in the absence (a), and presence
548 of 0.65 mM L-lactate where MoS₂, of 90 nm particle size, has been exfoliated in
549 IPA/water (b), EtOH/water (c), DMF (d) and NMP (e). Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹.

550
551 **Figure 2.** CV response of GC electrodes modified with MoS₂ (exfoliated in NMP) and
552 LOx in contact with 0.1 M pH = 7 phosphate buffer containing 1 mM of HMF in the
553 absence (a), and presence of 0.65 mM L-lactate where MoS₂ has a particle size of 2 μm
554 (b) and 90 nm (c). Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹.

555
556 **Figure 3.** Intensities of the anodic peak current obtained from cyclic voltammetric
557 measurements at +0.30 V for GC electrodes modified with different concentrations of
558 90 nm MoS₂ in NMP. [HMF] = 1 mM in 0.1 M pH = 7 phosphate buffer. [L-lactate] =
559 0.25 mM. Other conditions: scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹.

560
561 **Figure 4.** (a) 10 x 10 μm² AFM image of a sample prepared by depositing a drop of
562 NMP on silicon and let it to dry. (b) 2.5 x 2.5 μm² topographical AFM image of a
563 sample containing MoS₂ exfoliated in NMP. (c) Surface profile corresponding to the
564 solid line in (b). Topographical (d) and KFM (e) 2 x 2 μm² images taken
565 simultaneously on an area displaying a flake. The vertical scale in the KFM image
566 corresponds to the CPD signal. Note the different contrast in the KFM image at the
567 flake. (f) 480 x 360 nm² AFM image of a sample with MoS₂ exfoliated in NMP and
568 with LOx. (g) Surface profile along the line depicted in (f). (h) 360 x 360 nm² AFM
569 taken in other location of the sample imaged in (f).

570
571 **Figure 5.** Electrochemical impedance spectra obtained in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH
572 = 7), containing 10 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} for: (a) GC bare, (b) GC/LOx, (c) GC/MoS₂/LOx
573 and (d) GC/MoS₂ systems. The inset corresponds to an amplification of curve a.

574
575 **Figure 6. A.** Cyclic voltammograms obtained for 1 mM HMF in presence of different
576 concentrations of lactate (expressed in mM): (a) 0.050, (b) 0.149, (c) 0.247, (d) 0.344,
577 (e) 0.440, (f) 0.582, (g) 0.676 and (h) 0.769. Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹. **B.** Calibration curve
578 obtained from current intensity measured at +0.30 V. The inset shows the linear
579 concentration range.

MoS₂ nanosheets for improving analytical performance of lactate biosensors

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

- ✓ Integration of MoS₂ nanosheets and lactate oxidase enzyme in 2D biosensors
- ✓ MoS₂ nanosheets are obtained by a liquid exfoliation method
- ✓ Biosensors containing both components exhibit the best electrocatalytic response

SCHEME 1

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

Table 1

REFERENCE	ELECTRODE MODIFICATION	LINEAR CONCENTRATION RANGE (mM)	SENSITIVITY (μAmM^{-1})	DETECTION LIMIT (μM)	R.S.D. (%)
Present work	GC/MoS ₂ /LOx	0.056 - 0.77	6.22	17	1.7 (n=10)
[35]	Au/MPTS/AuNPs/LOx	0.05 -0.25	3.4	4.0	2 (n=10)
[36]	LOx/PtNPs/GCNF/SPCEs	0.01 - 2.0	0.0413 *	6.9	1.8 (n=10)
[37]	LOx/AuNPs/ZnO NRs/Au	0.01 - 0.6	24.56 *	6	4.23 (n=5)
[38]	Au /DNPs9/ LOx	0.05 -0.7	4.0	15	5 (n=9)
[39]	Au/ DNPs4/LOx	0.02 -1.2	6.1	5.3	1 (n=50)
[40]	Au/MPTS/DNPs9/LOx	0.053 -1.6	2.6	16	7.0 (n=3)
[41]	GC/GO/LOx	0.018 -0.58	6.5	5.5	3.0 (n=5)
[41]	GC/ERG/LOx	0.025 -0.25	3.2	7.5	6.1 (n=5)
[42]	LDH/Fe ₃ O ₄ /r-GO/GC	0.2 -2.2	22.6 *	20	-----
[43]	GC/PRG/TiO ₂ /LOx	0.002 -0.40	6.0	0.60	3.2 (n=5)
[44]	LDH/ r-GO/AuNPs/SPCEs	0.01 -5	154 *	0.13	1.57 (n=20)
[45]	LDH/ rGO- PhNHOH/GC	Up to 0.090	10.57 *	2.5	-----
[46]	LOx/N-CNTs/GC	0.014 -0.325	40 *	4.1	1.6 (n=10)
[47]	LOx/BCC/MWCNTs/CPE	0.0002 -0.11	-----	0.07	2.5 (n=7)
[48]	MWCNTs/CS/LOx/SPBGE	0.03 -0.24	3.417	22.6	5 (n=7)

Table 1. Analytical properties of lactate biosensors found in the literature

Glassy carbon (GC); Molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂); Lactate oxidase (LOx); (3-mercaptopropyl)-trimethoxysilane (MPTS); gold nanoparticles (AuNPs); platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs); graphitized carbon nanofibers (GCNF); screen printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs); zinc oxide nanorods (ZnO NRs); diamond nanoparticles of 9 nm (DNPs9); diamond nanoparticles of 4 nm (DNPs4); graphene oxide (GO); electrochemically reduced graphene (ERG); Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH); Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄); reduced graphene oxide (r-GO); photocatalytically reduced graphene (PRG); TiO₂ nanoparticles (TiO₂); derivatized reduced graphene oxide (r-GO-PhNHOH); Nitrogen-doped carbon nanotubes (N-CNTs); Benzo[c]cinnoline (BCC); multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs); carbon paste electrode (CPE); chitosan (CS); basal-plane like screen-printed graphite electrodes (SPBGEs); *sensitivity value normalized by cm²

Table 2. Interferences study ([lactate] = 0.25 mM).

Potential Interferent	Ratio [Interferent]/[Lactate]	ΔI (%)
Dopamine	0.25	12
Ascorbic acid	0.53	11
Uric acid	1.0	13
Citric acid	3.0	11

Biographies

Ana María Parra-Alfambra received her degree in Analytical Chemistry and her PhD degree from Universidad Autónoma de Madrid in 2000 and 2008, respectively. Since 2013 she is Associate Professor in the Department of Analytical Chemistry and Instrumental Analysis at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Her current research interests consist of the incorporation of different nanomaterials in the development of electrochemical biosensors.

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Carmen Quintana received her degree in Chemistry in 1991 from the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid and her PhD degree in 1998 from the same University. Since 2010 she is Professor at the Department of Analytical Chemistry and Instrumental Analysis at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Her current research is focused on the development and characterization of electrochemical sensors based on macrocyclic receptors and different nanomaterials (i.e. gold nanoparticles or graphene among others).

Maria del Pozo received her degree and PhD degree in Chemistry from the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain) in 2008 and 2013, respectively. Afterwards,

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